

STUDIES IN ORGANO-ARSENIC COMPOUNDS. PART IV. HETEROCYCLIC RING CONTAINING ARSENIC.

BY HIRENDRA NATH DAS-GUPTA.

Only a few heterocyclic compounds containing arsenic in the ring are known. It appears from literature that no attempt has hitherto been made to synthesise the arsenic analogue of indole. The synthesis of a compound of this type was thought to be interesting not only from theoretical point of view but also from the expected therapeutic activity.*

1-Chloroarsindole has now been synthesised in various ways but the present communication deals with its preparation directly from benzene and β -chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine (Green and Price, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 448). Two distinct types of compounds, *viz.*, (i) β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine and, (ii) β -chlorovinyl-diphenylarsine are formed along with a large quantity of liquid and solid by-products by the condensation of benzene and β -chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine either alone at a high temperature or in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride at room temperature. The by-products obtained are of diverse types, but only two could be isolated namely, (a) yellow crystals (m.p. 170°) but containing no arsenic, and (b) a violet noncrystallisable compound containing arsenic. The identity of either compound could not be ascertained.

* Results of preliminary experiments were hopeful and the procedure to be adopted was published (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1933, p. 169). Mannich (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1935: 273, 275), while studying the action of arsenic trichloride on 1-phenyl-3-diethylamino-propine, obtained two different types of compounds, one of them being a derivative of arsindole and took no notice of the publication referred to above and consequently a note was published by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 627).

The synthesis of secondary and tertiary arsines by the above method is not uncommon. Thus benzene and arsenic trichloride give primary and secondary arsines (*cf.* La Coste and Michaelis, *Ber.*, 1878, 11, 1883; *Annalen*, 1880, 201, 184). La Coste (*Inaug. Dissert., Freiburg*, 1879) and Wieland (*Annalen*, 1923, 431, 30) have shown that the Friedel-Craft's reaction may be used for the preparation of primary, secondary, and tertiary arsines, the yield of the last one being the maximum.

The analytical data of compounds (I) and (II) are in close agreement with the theoretically calculated figures. To corroborate further the correctness of the structure of the above compounds the following syntheses were effected :

In each case a tertiary arsine has been obtained which readily gives a solid mercuric chloride double compound of the type $\text{Ph}_2\text{As} \cdot \text{CH} = \text{CHCl}$, HgCl_2 having identical properties.

The conversion of β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine into 1-chloroarsindole was effected by heating in dry carbon disulphide with aluminium chloride. The reaction is vigorous without any solvent and a reddish violet product of an indefinite nature is formed.

Besides the analytical data the correctness of the structure of 1-chloroarsindole was established by oxidising it with dilute nitric acid to *o*-carboxyphenylarsonic acid (*cf.* Lewis and Cheetham, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 510; Bert, *Annalen*, 1922, 429, 86, 111; G. P. 250264; Aeschlimann and McClelland, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 128, 2025; Rosenmund, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 438). The *o*-carboxyphenylarsonic acid does not melt up to 320° and

its identity with that obtained from the usual sources was proved by its conversion into oxide and also hydrolysing the oxide to benzoic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Interaction of Benzene and β -Chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine.—The operation was conducted with or without aluminium chloride as follows:

(i) A mixture of β -chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine (30 g.), dry benzene (10 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (7 g.) in a flask, fitted with condenser and calcium chloride guard tube, was allowed to stand for some time when there was evolution of hydrogen chloride with rise in temperature. The reaction was moderated by cooling the flask with ice-cold water. Occasionally application of heat was required to start the reaction. The deep brown reaction product was allowed to remain for 2 hours. It was next decomposed with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the viscous brown product, thus obtained, was extracted first with ether and then with carbon tetrachloride. The extracts contained a violet solid which was removed. The ethereal extract was washed successively with cold dilute sodium carbonate solution, dilute hydrochloric acid and water, dried over calcium chloride. The solvent was nearly evaporated off, and the solution treated with ether when a precipitate was formed which was crystallised from acetone in needles. m.p. 170° (decomp.); as it contained no arsenic its identity was not sought for. It gives fluorescence with alcohol. The solvent was removed from the solution and the oil was fractionated. The principal fractions collected were at (a) $130-150^{\circ}/5$ mm. and (b) $180-200^{\circ}/5$ mm.

(ii) A mixture of benzene (25 c.c.) and β -chlorovinyl-dichloroarsine (35 c.c.) was refluxed at $150-60^{\circ}$ for 36 hours and the resulting product was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed as described above and the oil obtained was fractionated. Two fractions were collected (1) at $128-148^{\circ}/4$ mm., (2) $178-195^{\circ}/4$ mm.

β -Chlorovinyl-phenylchloroarsine.—The fraction, b.p. $130-150/5$ mm. was redistilled *in vacuo* through a long fractionating column when a light yellow product was obtained, b.p. $138-42^{\circ}/3$ mm. It was identified and proved to be analogous to the compound obtained from phenyl-dichloroarsine and acetylene (to be communicated later) by its conversion into the acid and determining the mixed m.p. The compound possesses an unpleasant odour but is not so irritant as the parent substance. [Found: C, 38.1; H, 2.5; Cl, 28.4; As, 30.3; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 246.8. Calc. for $C_8H_7Cl_2As$: C, 38.5; H, 2.8; Cl, 28.5; As 30.12 per cent. M. W., 249].

β -Chlorovinyl-diphenylarsine.—The fraction, b.p. $180-210^{\circ}/5$ mm., was redistilled at $190-98^{\circ}/3$ mm. as a yellow viscous oil. This was identified

by its synthesis from bromobenzene and β -chlorovinylidichloroarsine.

To the Grignard reagent from bromobenzene (15 g.), magnesium (2.4 g.) in absolute ether (100 c.c.), β -chlorovinylidichloroarsine (10 g.) in dry ether was added drop by drop with shaking. The reaction mixture was heated for 1 hour on a water-bath, cooled and decomposed by ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The ethereal layer was removed and the aqueous layer extracted with more ether. The extracts were washed successively with dilute sodium hydroxide solution, dilute hydrochloric acid and water and was dried over fused calcium chloride; the ether evaporated off in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide and the residual oil was distilled at 198-205°/3 mm. During distillation white fumes were evolved and solid particles were found to be deposited on the delivery tube. The distillate was turbid and it was found to be insoluble in alcohol. It was shaken with excess of alcohol, and the lower layer was removed, dissolved in ether and filtered. The ether from the filtrate was evaporated off and the liquid distilled. The fraction (small in quantity) up to 195°/3 mm. was collected separately and the main bulk distilled at 195-98°/3 mm. In a similar manner this compound was prepared from phenyl magnesium bromide and β -chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine.

It is a viscous yellow oil possessing slightly offensive odour. It causes blister on the skin. [Found: C, 57.6; H, 3.9; Cl, 12.5; As, 25.2; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 288.9. $C_{14}H_{12}Cl_2As$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.1; Cl, 12.2; As, 25.8 per cent. M.W., 290.5].

β -Chlorovinylidiphenylarsine Mercuric Chloride.—On mixing molecular proportions of β -chlorovinylidiphenylarsine and mercuric chloride in ether a white precipitate appeared which was filtered off, finely powdered and washed with excess of ether. It was dissolved in chloroform and precipitated by ether and was crystallised from excess of alcohol, m.p. 238°. The mixed melting point of this compound and that prepared from benzene and β -chlorovinylidichloroarsine was also found to be 238°. (Found: Hg, 35.5. $C_{14}H_{12}Cl_2As$ Hg requires Hg, 35.6 per cent).

1-Chloroarsindole.— β -Chlorovinylphenylchloroarsine (22 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g.) were dissolved in absolute carbon disulphide and heated for 7 hours. The evolution of hydrogen chloride was slow and uniform throughout this period and the colour of the mixture changed to deep brown. On keeping the reaction mixture overnight, two layers separated, the lower one being deep brown in colour and the upper one colourless. The mixture was decomposed by dilute hydrochloric acid. The carbon disulphide layer was separated and the acid layer was extracted several times first with carbon

tetrachloride and then with ether. The different extracts were filtered and the solvents evaporated off in an atmosphere of CO_2 under reduced pressure. The residual brown oil was distilled at $100\text{-}75^\circ/6$ mm. This was redistilled and the following fractions were collected: (a) $100\text{-}125^\circ/3$ mm. (light oil, 1 c.c.); (b) $130\text{-}145^\circ$ (yellow oil, 63.5 c.c.). The fraction, b.p. $130\text{-}45^\circ$, was redistilled using a long fractionating column when a light yellow oil was obtained at $128\text{-}35^\circ/3$ mm. It has a very penetrating odour and has a very strong corrosive action on the skin. The compound is found to be soluble in the common organic solvents. It darkens when kept exposed to the action of light. [Found: C, 44.9; H, 2.7; Cl, 16.3; As, 35.5; M.W. (cryoscopic in benzene), 215; $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{ClAs}$ requires C, 45.1; H, 2.8; Cl, 16.7; As, 35.2 per cent. M.W., 212.5].

1-Methylarsindole.

To the magnesium compound from methyl iodide (4 g.) magnesium (0.6 g) and dry ether (40 c.c.). 1-chloroarsindole (5 g.) in ether was added drop by drop. The resulting mixture was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours and allowed to stand overnight. The mixture was decomposed with water and dilute hydrochloric acid. The yellow ethereal layer was removed and the coloured aqueous layer was extracted several times with ether till it was perfectly colourless. The ethereal solution was filtered and the ether evaporated off when a golden yellow oil was obtained possessing the characteristic smell of phenyl mustard oil. This was distilled at $142\text{-}45^\circ/6$ mm. [Found: C, 55.9; H, 4.8; As, 38.8; M.W. (cryoscopic), 189. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_9\text{As}$ requires C, 56.2; H, 4.6; As, 39.06 per cent. M.W., 192].

1-Dimethyliodoarsindole.

1-Methylarsindole was heated for 1 hour on a water-bath with excess of methyl iodide, when crystals separated. The crystals were collected and crystallised from alcohol in yellow beautiful needles. It decomposes at 216-18° but does not melt upto 320°. (Found: As, 22.4. $C_{10}H_{12}IAs$ requires As, 22.4 per cent).

1-Methylarsindole Mercuric Chloride.—An ethereal solution of 1-methylarsindole was added to molecular proportion of mercuric chloride in the same solvent. The white precipitate was repeatedly washed with ether, dried and crystallised from alcohol in white silky needles, m.p. 150-51°. (Found: Hg, 43.03. $C_9H_9Cl_2As$ Hg requires Hg, 43.1 per cent).

Oxidation of 1-Chloroarsindole.—1-Chloroarsindole was treated with excess of dilute nitric acid (60%). When the vigorous reaction subsided the reaction mixture was heated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and *o*-carboxyphenylarsonic acid was precipitated by dilute hydrochloric acid as a colourless solid. It was crystallised from water as colourless glistening plates, not melting up to 320°. It was converted into oxide by reducing the aqueous solution of the acid by SO_2 and HI at 60° and also hydrolysing the oxide to benzoic acid.

My thanks are due to Dr. M. Goswami and to Mr. B. C. Ray for their keen interest in this investigation.

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 17, 1937.